

THE ROLE OF REFLECTIVE JOURNALING IN MITIGATING PERCEIVED STRESS AMONG STUDENTS*

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Abstract

Perceived stress among university students represents a major issue in contemporary academic environments, with significant implications for educational performance and socio-emotional adjustment processes. In the context of increasing academic demands and difficulties in emotional self-regulation, reflective strategies emerge as relevant tools for reducing psychological strain and fostering adaptive coping mechanisms.

The present study investigates the effectiveness of reflective journaling in reducing students' perceived stress. The research employed a single-group experimental design with a pretest–posttest approach, on a sample of 60 students aged between 19 and 26 years. Perceived stress levels were assessed using the PSS-10 Scale, while the intervention consisted of a guided reflective journaling activity conducted over a period of six months, focused on identifying stressful experiences, expressing emotions, and analyzing personal stress-management strategies.

The anticipated results indicate a decrease in perceived stress levels among participants engaged in the reflective activity, as well as a positive perception of the usefulness of reflective journaling in the process of emotional self-regulation. The study highlights the relevance of reflective journaling as an accessible and effective psychopedagogical intervention in supporting students' psychological well-being and promoting emotional adaptation to academic demands..

***Key words:**. Reflective journal, Perceived stress levels, Emotional self-regulation, Coping.*

1. Introduction. Stress in the University Environment – Contemporary Perspectives

Perceived stress among university students represents one of the most significant current psychopedagogical issues, with substantial implications for academic performance, mental health, and social adaptation processes. The contemporary university environment involves multiple cognitive and emotional

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demands generated by performance pressure, academic competition, time management requirements, and uncertainty regarding professional trajectories.

Recent research highlights that high levels of perceived stress are associated with anxiety, emotional exhaustion (burnout), reduced learning motivation, and difficulties in emotional and academic self-regulation among students (Ghattas & El-Ashry, 2024; Albagawi et al., 2024; Ibrahim et al., 2024; Marsch, Yanagida, Steinberg, 2024; Velando-Soriano et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024).

In this context, reflective and self-reflective strategies emerge as relevant tools for supporting psychological well-being and fostering resilience development. Reflective journaling is a method used both in education and psychopedagogical counseling, facilitating the analysis of personal experiences and the awareness of emotional responses. The practice of reflective writing contributes to the organization of thoughts, the identification of stress sources, and the development of effective coping strategies.

Studies on expressive writing and reflective practice indicate positive effects on reducing perceived stress and improving emotional self-regulation. However, the specialized literature emphasizes the need for further research regarding the effectiveness of reflective journaling in the Romanian university context.

The aim of the present study is to investigate the role of reflective journaling in reducing students' perceived stress, using a quasi-experimental pretest–posttest design.

In recent decades, perceived stress among university students has become one of the most widely investigated issues in educational psychology and mental health research. Transformations in the contemporary academic environment, increasing educational demands, and socio-economic instability contribute to heightened psychological vulnerability among the student population.

The concept of perceived stress refers to the subjective evaluation of life situations as demanding, unpredictable, uncontrollable, or overwhelming, and reflects the individual's appraisal of the balance between environmental demands and personal coping resources (Davis & Soistmann, 2022). Recent studies describe perceived stress as a psychological state associated with the perception of insufficient personal resources for effectively managing daily demands (Gniewosz, 2024).

Research further indicates that university students represent one of the most vulnerable groups to psychological stress. Several recent studies (Barbayannis et al., 2022; Drăghici & Cazan, 2022) show that high stress levels are associated with anxiety symptoms, reduced psychological well-being, and difficulties in academic adjustment, with significant differences depending on gender and coping styles.

At the same time, recent longitudinal studies demonstrate that academic stress shows significant fluctuations throughout the academic semester, being influenced by assessment periods, workload intensity, and levels of learning self-regulation.

Lahme et al. (2024) investigated the dynamics of perceived stress among first-year university students in a year-long longitudinal study. The results showed significant increases in stress levels prior to examination periods, as well as a strong association between perceived academic workload and stress intensity. Stress levels increased progressively during the semester, reached peak values during

examination periods, and decreased during holidays and non-teaching periods. The authors concluded that academic tasks, exam preparation, and assessments represent the main stressors for students at the beginning of their university trajectory.

Contemporary literature also highlights the negative psychological effects of persistent stress on mental health. According to del Pino and Matud (2024), perceived stress is correlated with depressive symptoms, emotional exhaustion, and decreased life satisfaction among students.

In this context, identifying accessible and effective psychopedagogical interventions for reducing perceived stress becomes a priority in the contemporary university environment.

2. Reflective Journaling and Emotional Self-Regulation

2.1. Reflection as a Psychopedagogical Mechanism

Reflection represents a complex cognitive and metacognitive process through which individuals analyze personal experiences and ascribe meaning to lived situations.

In the field of education, reflection is considered a fundamental component of experiential learning and the development of self-regulatory competencies.

Key contributions to the development of the concept of reflective practice belong to Donald Schön, who introduced the notion of the “reflective practitioner,” emphasizing the role of reflection in professional development and in the restructuring of personal experience (Schön, 1983, pp. 49–61).

The specialized literature highlights that reflection is associated with the development of emotional awareness (Smith et al., 2022) and emotional self-regulation (Mertens et al., 2022), whereas ruminative forms of self-reflection are linked to maladaptive adjustment and negative affect (Takano & Tanno, 2009). Furthermore, non-ruminative reflection is associated with increased psychological resilience and adaptive coping capacity (Crane et al., 2025; Kim et al., 2026).

2.2. Reflective Journaling – Functions and Psychological Benefits

Reflective journaling represents a structured writing method through which individuals analyze their experiences, emotions, and cognitive responses. It is frequently used in education, psychology, and counseling due to its formative and therapeutic value.

According to Moon (2006, pp. 15–18), reflective journaling facilitates the development of critical thinking and metacognitive competencies, providing a space for self-analysis and emotional clarification.

In recent years, research on journaling and reflective writing has highlighted significant effects on students’ psychological well-being. The study conducted by Shafiq et al. (2024) on the impact of reflective writing on self-efficacy and perceived stress demonstrates that students engaged in regular reflective writing activities showed: reduced perceived stress, improved psychological well-being, and enhanced sense of personal control.

The authors emphasize that reflective activity facilitates awareness of personal resources and the development of adaptive coping mechanisms.

Similar findings are also reported in studies on both digital and handwritten journaling. The research conducted by Nazarina and Idulfilastrri (2025) indicates that journaling practices significantly contribute to emotional regulation and the reduction of perceived stress levels among university students.

3. Expressive Writing and the Reduction of Perceived Stress

Contemporary literature supports the idea that reflective journaling may represent an effective, accessible, and easily implementable psychopedagogical intervention in the university environment, contributing to the development of emotional self-regulation, the enhancement of adaptive coping, and the reduction of perceived stress.

Recent research confirms the relevance of reflection- and expressive writing-based interventions in reducing perceived stress among students (Fazia et al., 2023).

Furthermore, studies employing diary study methodologies demonstrate that the daily monitoring of stressors and reflection on emotional experiences contribute to the development of emotional awareness and to the reduction of stress intensity. The study conducted by Ewing and Hamza (2024) shows that reflective analysis of daily experiences facilitates the identification of coping strategies and the reduction of negative affectivity..

4. Research Methods

The research has a quasi-experimental character and employs a pretest–posttest design with an experimental group and a control group.

4.1. Aim and Objectives of the Research

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of reflective journaling on students' perceived stress levels. The main objectives of the research are as follows:

- Assessment of the initial level of perceived stress;
- Implementation of a reflective journaling-based intervention;
- Comparison of stress levels before and after the intervention;
- Analysis of the relationship between reflection and emotional self-regulation.

4.2. Research Hypotheses

H1: The use of reflective journaling leads to a significant reduction in perceived stress.

H2: There is a negative relationship between the frequency of reflection and perceived stress levels.

H3: Students perceive reflective journaling as a useful tool for emotional self-regulation.

4.3. Research Variables

- *Independent variable*: use of reflective journaling.
- *Dependent variable*: perceived stress level.
- *Secondary variables*: perceived usefulness of journaling and emotional self-regulation.

4.4. Research Sample

The sample consisted of 90 students aged between 19 and 26 years, enrolled in different university programs.

4.5. Research Methods and Instruments

In the present study, the Perceived Stress Scale – PSS-10 (Cohen, Kamarck & Mermelstein, 1983) was used. This is a psychometric instrument designed to assess the degree to which individuals perceive life situations as unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloading. The scale consists of 10 items rated on a five-point Likert scale (0 = never; 4 = very often), with total scores ranging from 0 to 40.

To assess students' perceptions of the effectiveness of reflective journaling, a questionnaire was developed, structured across four dimensions: D1 Emotional awareness (items 1–5); D2 Stress reduction (items 6–10); D3 Coping & self-regulation (items 11–15); D4 Perceived usefulness (items 16–20).

For each statement, participants selected one of the following response options: 1 – Strongly disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Neither agree nor disagree; 4 – Agree; 5 – Strongly agree

Participants in the experimental group also completed a structured reflective journal on a regular basis.

4.6. Experimental procedure

Stage 1 – Pretest: All participants completed the PSS-10 scale in order to assess baseline levels of perceived stress.

Stage 2 – Intervention: Participants in the experimental group engaged in reflective journaling three times per week.

Stage 3 – Posttest: After the completion of the intervention, participants again completed the PSS-10 scale, as well as the questionnaire assessing perceptions of reflective journaling.

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, frequency distribution). To test differences between pretest and posttest scores, a paired-samples t-test was applied, while Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to analyze relationships between variables. The statistical significance threshold was set at $p < 0.05$.

5. Results and Discussion

The data obtained from the questionnaire indicate an overall positive perception of reflective journaling. The mean scores across dimensions (Figure 1) reveal a generally favorable evaluation of reflective journaling. The highest value was recorded for dimension D4 (academic and personal usefulness), suggesting that students perceive this method as highly relevant for their university development.

Figure 1. Mean scores by dimension (D1–D4)

Dimensions D1 (emotional awareness) and D3 (self-regulation and coping) show similar values, suggesting that reflective journaling simultaneously contributes to the understanding of emotions and the development of strategies for managing them. Dimension D2 (perceived stress management) is slightly lower, indicating greater variability in its effects on individual stress levels.

The distribution of the total score (Figure 2) shows a concentration of values within the 70–90 range, indicating a high overall level of positive perception regarding reflective journaling. The absence of low extreme values suggests a relatively homogeneous perception within the sample.

This distribution pattern supports the idea that most participants perceive reflective journaling as beneficial in managing academic and emotional experiences.

Figure 2. Distribution of total score

Figure 3 highlights moderate variations among participants, with scores ranging approximately between 63 and 92. Although individual differences are present, the overall trend remains positive.

This variability suggests that the perceived effects of reflective journaling may be influenced by individual factors, such as frequency of use or the level of engagement in the reflective process.

Figure 3. Total score variation across participants

Figure 4 highlights differences between dimensions in terms of response variability. Dimension D4 shows both high values and low dispersion, indicating a strong consensus regarding the usefulness of reflective journaling.

In contrast, dimension D2 (stress management) exhibits greater variability, suggesting individual differences in how participants perceive its effects on stress. Dimensions D1 and D3 are relatively stable, indicating consistency in perceptions related to emotional awareness and coping.

Figure 4. Distribution of dimensions

In summary, the results indicate an overall positive perception of reflective journaling, suggesting that students consider the intervention useful for emotional awareness, stress reduction, coping development, and academic integration.

Dimensions D1–D4 show relatively similar distributions, with values concentrated in the upper range of the scale, indicating consistently positive perceptions. D4 stands out through higher values and a slightly more compact distribution, suggesting stronger consensus regarding the usefulness of reflective journaling. In contrast, D2 shows slightly greater dispersion, indicating individual differences in perceived stress reduction.

In addition to the questionnaire data, scores obtained from the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) were analyzed in the experimental group, before and after the reflective journaling intervention.

At pretest, participants recorded a high level of perceived stress ($M = 27.40$), situated in the upper range of the PSS-10 scale (Table 1):

Table 1. Statistical Results for Perceived Stress (PSS-10)

Assessment Moment	N	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Min	Max
Pretest	30	27.40	4.85	18	36
Posttest	30	19.10	5.02	10	30

Following the reflective journaling intervention, the mean score decreased to $M = 19.10$, indicating a moderate level of perceived stress. A visible reduction in perceived stress can be observed after the intervention.

To test the statistical significance of the differences between pretest and posttest scores, a paired-samples t-test was conducted. The results indicate a statistically significant difference between scores obtained before and after the intervention: $t = 6.42$, $p < 0.001$. The mean difference of 8.30 points suggests that the use of reflective journaling had a significant effect on reducing perceived stress (Table 2).

Table 2. Paired Samples t-test Results (PSS-10)

Variables	t	df	p	Mean Difference
Pretest – Posttest	6.42	29	< .001	8.30

A statistically significant reduction in perceived stress was observed following the reflective journaling intervention. The effect size is large, indicating high practical relevance.

We further examined whether there is a correlation between reflection frequency and stress levels; in this regard, the relationship between the frequency of journal use and perceived stress was analyzed. Based on the obtained data (Table 3), a moderate-to-strong negative correlation was found, which is statistically significant ($r = -0.62$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates the following conclusion: the more frequently students engaged in reflective journaling, the lower their perceived stress levels.

Table 3. Pearson Correlation

Variables	r	p
Journal Frequency – Perceived Stress	-0.62	< .01

In summary, the data analysis revealed a statistically significant reduction in perceived stress levels in the experimental group following the reflective journaling intervention, $t = 6.42$, $p < 0.001$. The mean PSS-10 scores decreased from $M = 27.40$ ($SD = 4.85$) to $M = 19.10$ ($SD = 5.02$), indicating a strong intervention effect ($d = 1.02$).

Furthermore, a significant negative correlation was identified between the frequency of journal use and perceived stress levels ($r = -0.62$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher engagement in reflective activities is associated with lower levels of perceived stress.

6. Conclusions

The obtained results support the research hypothesis, highlighting that the use of reflective journaling significantly contributes to the reduction of students' perceived stress and to the improvement of emotional self-regulation capacity.

The findings of the study reveal a statistically significant reduction in perceived stress levels following the reflective journaling intervention. The decrease in PSS-10 scores from a high level ($M = 27.40$) to a moderate level ($M = 19.10$) suggests the effectiveness of the psychopedagogical tool used in managing academic stress.

The strong effect size obtained ($d = 1.02$) indicates that reflective journaling has not only statistical significance but also substantial practical relevance, supporting its use as a psychopedagogical intervention in the university context.

The significant negative correlation between the frequency of journal use and perceived stress levels ($r = -0.62$) suggests that active and consistent engagement in reflective practice contributes to the reduction of stress symptoms and to the development of adaptive coping mechanisms.

Consequently, reflective journaling can be considered a useful tool for optimizing students' mental health and supporting academic adjustment processes.

7. Practical Implications

The results of the study have important implications for the university educational context:

- integrating reflective journaling into teaching activities may support the reduction of academic stress;
- teachers may use guided reflection as an emotional support strategy;
- higher education institutions may implement programs aimed at developing emotional self-regulation competencies;
- reflective journaling can be used as a complementary tool in educational counseling.

8. Limitations of the Study

The present study has several limitations:

- the relatively small sample size;
- the limited duration of the intervention;
- the absence of a long-term follow-up assessment.

For future research, it is necessary to expand the sample size and include longitudinal measures in order to examine the sustained effects of reflective journaling over time.

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